

Title: Adhesive behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced plastic panels manufactured using woven and unidirectional tape after ultraviolet laser surface treatment

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Abstract

This paper describes the results obtained when ultraviolet laser treatment was performed as a surface treatment prior to adhesive bonding for two aeronautical carbon fibre-reinforced plastics based on an epoxy resin prepreg. Different laser- processing parameters were employed, and their effect on the surfaces was analysed through morphological character- isation and wettability studies. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements were performed to determine the cleaning and activation effects of the treatment. The strength of the bonded joint was studied for laser-treated and manually ground samples. Samples processed under the selected laser conditions exhibited better adhesive behaviour than the manually treated samples, thereby suggesting that ultraviolet laser treatment could be used as an alternative method for surface activation of aeronautical composites based on epoxy resins.

Keywords

Composites, surface treatment, adhesive joint, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, UV-laser

Introduction

In recent years, there has been an exponential increase in the use of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) in aeronautical manufacturing, and the most frequently employed technique to join the carbon fibre elements is the mechanical joining with mechanical fasteners. However, the use of these fasteners has several drawbacks: it requires the drilling of laminates prior to using fasteners, which can damage the fibres; it increases the weight of the structure, and allows for galvanic corrosion. Furthermore, this process is a time-consuming manual method that presents a lack of robustness owing to the use of human labour. For these reasons, the use of adhesive bonding arises as an alternative option for the joining operations to overcome the above mentioned problems.¹

The use of adhesive bonding on primary structures is still limited in the aeronautical sector. This limita- tion arises from the difficulties of industrialisation of pure adhesive-bonded primary structures. The main

drawback of adhesive bonding is that it may contain defects that could act as crack sources, which could lead to mechanical breakdown of the joint.¹

To date, the normal practice in the aeronautical sector for these types of elements is to adhesive bonding reinforced with mechanical fixation elements such as rivets, which reduces the benefits that could be obtained from the use of pure adhesive bonding.

According to aeronautical standards, the adhesive bonding of CFRP elements requires an initial step of surface preparation.² The aim of this treatment is to remove surface contaminants such as the residues

from mould release agents that remain from the manufacturing process, and to obtain a clean, slightly rough and active surface.¹ Some methods presently employed and identified in the literature are peel-ply, sandpapering, manual grinding or chemical attack.³⁻⁷ All these techniques show different limitations to some extent. After peel-ply removal, a thin resin film remains on the surface of the material; hence the adhesive bonds to this layer and not directly to the fibres, which implies the existence of a weak layer that hinders the direct transmission of force into the fibre.⁸ Manual grinding and sand blasting pose a significant risk of damaging the fibres. Further, they are manual methods that depend on the operator skill, and they require a second-ary cleaning step to remove contamination created by the preparation process itself.⁸ Chemical attacks are based on the use of solvents, strong acids, or bases, which result in the environmental hazards. Furthermore, all these methods have a shared limitation: they are not automatable.

In this context, one of the main goals of the aeronautical sector is to find new automatable methods that can be substituted for manual ones. Two technologies are gaining acceptance: atmospheric pressure plasma (APP) systems⁹⁻¹³ and laser technologies.^{8,14-20} APP systems use a high-frequency pulsed current, which, in combination with the flow of clean compressed air, generates highly reactive APP species. These species oxidise the treated surface and create functional groups that increase the adhesive properties of the surface. Different studies⁹⁻¹³ have demonstrated that APP surface treatment leads to high-strength adhesive bonding. Furthermore, this technology shows high throughput in-line manufacturing process capabilities, high possibilities of automation and relatively low processing costs. All these arguments suggest that APP systems are a good alternative to manual methods for surface preparation.

Another alternative method that is gaining acceptance is the use of laser radiation.^{8,14-20} This method is a non-contact technique, it is controllable and automatable and it is environmentally friendly. In addition, this technology permits a selective removal of resin without damaging the fibres via controlling the processing parameters. This process involves the removal of contaminants, which enhances the quality of the adhesive bonding.

Depending on the wavelength of the radiation used, different phenomena can occur.⁸ On one hand, a photo-thermal process occurs under exposure to radiation of long wavelengths ($\lambda \geq 1060$ nm). This radiation is not sufficiently energetic to break chemical bonds (E_p & 0.12 eV), but it heats the surface, thus causing thermal damage. On the other hand, the photochemical process occurs under exposure to short wavelength radiation ($\lambda < 355$ nm). In this case, photons are

energetic enough (E_p & 3.49 eV) to break molecular bonds, as reflected in the higher reactivity of the treated surface.

Laser sources have been used in composite materials to perform mechanisation tasks,^{16,18,20} repair operations^{17,19} or surface activation.^{8,14} In a study by Kreling et al.^{14,15} the use of different excimer lasers was studied as a surface activation method. In a study by Fischer et al.,⁸ an investigation of the effect of using ultraviolet (UV) and CO₂ lasers to irradiate CFRP surfaces was performed. The results showed the possibility of employing this technique as a surface activation method.

The aim of this work was to perform the surface activation of two CFRP materials manufactured using woven and unidirectional tape, by using an UV laser. Thus, one of the major goals of the present work was to study the influence of the manufacturing process on UV laser surface treatment. For each material, the effectiveness of the UV laser surface treatment was determined based on mechanical tests. The behaviour of the bonded joint for both materials was compared with those of manually treated samples to verify that UV laser treatment complies with the aeronautical requirements.

Material and methods

Materials

Woven and unidirectional tape CFRP laminates, made of different preregs from Hexcel Composites, have been studied. Woven preregs samples are made by interlacing two orthogonal sets of yarns, whilst in unidirectional tape samples all the fibres are oriented on the same direction.²¹ Table 1 provides the main characteristics of both materials. Laminates are cured following the cure cycle specified on technical data sheet of both studied materials.²²

To form the adhesive joint, PL-780-1.05 M, an epoxy film adhesive with a mat carrier, from Henkel Corp was used. The secondary bonding process was carried out in a hot plate press using the curing cycle given in Table 2.

In this study, the tool side of the samples was studied.

This side was in contact with the manufacturing mould and thus with the release agent. Generally, these types of agents contaminate the surfaces of the composite material with silicone. Therefore, it is important to determine whether the surface treatment can reduce the level of silicone present on the surfaces of the samples.

Manual grinding

In this study, manually ground flat panels fabricated using both woven and unidirectional tape materials

Table 1. Properties of studied materials.

Material	Woven	Unidirectional tape
Commercial designation	HexPly 8552 AGP280-5 H	Hexply 8552 AS4
Fibre designation	AS4	AS4
Resin designation	8552	8552
Filament count/tow	3K	12K
Fibre density	1.77 g/cm ³	1.79 g/cm ³
Fibre areal weight	280 g/m ²	194 g/m ²
Nominal fibre volume	55.29%	57.70%
Nominal laminate density	1.57 g/cm ³	1.57 g/cm ³
Laminate Layout	5 plies in 90° direction with weave of 5HS ^a	8 plies in 90° direction ^a
Laminate Thickness	1.2 mm	1.6 mm

^a90° with respect to long direction of laminates.

Table 2. Secondary bonding cure cycle conditions.

Curing time	99 min
Curing temperature	180°C
Applied pressure	300 kPa
Heating rate	2°C/min
Cooling rate	2°C/min

were used as reference samples. According to the AIPS06-01-003 study,² the surfaces were manually ground using 180-grit SiC paper. The samples were then rinsed with isopropyl alcohol (IPA) using a clean-dry cotton cloth until no dust appeared on them. The water break test showed a positive result for all the ground samples, which implies the cleanliness of the sample surfaces.

Laser processing

Surface treatments were conducted using a Trumpf UV laser, model TruMark6350 Nd:YAG solid-state frequency-tripled laser with a wavelength of 355 nm and a pulse duration of 11 ns. At 33 kHz, the nominal power reached was 5 W, the pulse power was more than 15 kW, and the pulse energy was 0.15 mJ. Based on this information and taking into account the fact that in the focal length (237 mm), the beam diameter was approximately 10 mm, the maximum energy density was calculated to be 193 J/cm². Samples were laser processed without any cleaning step prior to laser processing.

Table 3 shows the range of values of different laser parameters studied to evaluate their influence. For each parameter, a set of fixed values were studied: six power values, eight speeds, seven frequencies, four numbers of scans and three angular steps.²³ A total of 450 conditions have been processed.

Table 3. Range of studied parameters.

Parameter	Range
Power (P)	2.5-5 W
Processing speed (v)	50-3000 mm/s
Frequency (f)	20-80 kHz
Number of scans	1-8
Angular step ^a	0°, 45°, 90°

^aAngular step is defined as the increase of angle of radiation between consecutive scans.

Surface characterisation

The influence of the laser characteristic parameters on the surfaces of the samples was determined in two steps. In the first step, the influence of the beam power (P), frequency (f) and velocity (v) of processing was studied. In the second step, the influence of the number of scans and the angular steps of the marking direction was investigated.

Morphological characterisation was performed using a stereoscopic magnifier, model MST53 from Leica, obtaining pictures at magnifications of 11X, 20X and 72X. Contact angle measurements were performed with deionised water droplets of 5 mL with laboratory-made equipment using the 'Snake' plug-in of J-image software to measure the angle. These measurements were performed within 24 h after laser processing.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were acquired with an FEI Nova NanoSEM 650 microscope using different acquisition modes. On the one hand, images using a backscatter detector and applying 1 kV of landing energy (beam decelerator activated) were acquired at 2500X. On the other hand, images at 300X were taken with a low vacuum detector and an accelerating voltage of 5 kV.

The evaluation of surface roughness (R_a) was performed using a profilometer, model MarSurf PS10 from Mahr. These measurements were performed for untreated, manually ground and laser-treated samples.

The surface chemical changes that occurred because of the laser radiation were characterised via X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a KratosAxis Ultra DLD instrument equipped with a mono-chromatic source of X-rays and an anode of Al-K α ($h\nu$ $\frac{1}{4}$ 1486.6 eV).

Mechanical tests

The lap shear strength of the bonded samples was determined using a universal static testing machine, model AG-X from Shimadzu, with a capacity of 10 kN, according to the AITM 1-0019 study.²⁴ This standard describes how to calculate the tensile shear strength of a single lap joint. In this test, a load is applied continuously parallel to the axis of the test specimen until failure in shear mode in the overlap area occurs. This test was performed for five samples for each material and surface treatment, at a constant speed of 5000 N/min. The clamping method employed is described in the standard.

The mode I fracture toughness energy test was performed using a universal static testing machine, model 5982 from Instron, with a capacity of 100 kN,

according to the AITM 1-0053 study.²⁵ In this test, the fracture toughness energy of the samples is calculated as the energy necessary to produce a unit surface crack growth in a crack located at the joint. This test uses the area method to determine fracture toughness. The test speed was set to 10 mm/min and the hinge clamping method was used, according to AITM 1-0053 study.²⁵ Six samples for each material and surface treatment were tested.

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the test specimens used for each mechanical test.

Before performing the mechanical test, the bond line thicknesses of the adhesive bonded samples were measured to assess the homogeneity of all tested samples. Theoretically, this bond line thickness should be constant for all conditions, because the adhesive used had a mat carrier.²⁶ The bond line thickness was determined by optical microscopy visualisation of the cross sections of the tested samples.

After the mechanical tests, the failure modes of the tested samples were also determined.

Results and discussion

Surface morphological characterisation

Morphological characterisation of the laser-treated samples showed that different morphologies were

Figure 1. Schematic representation of mechanical test specimens: (a) lap shear strength test; (b) mode I fracture toughness test. All measurements are in millimetres.

obtained depending on the processing parameters. From the studied conditions, the samples treated with lower energies exhibited marked resin (Figure 2, WO1 and UT1). In these conditions, laser treatment only caused surface modification of the resin, leaving no exposed fibres. When the laser energy density was increased, strong interaction with the material occurred, leading to partial resin removal and locally exposed fibres (Figure 2, WO2 and UT2), full removal of the surface resin (Figure 2, WO3 and UT3) or marked fibres (Figure 2, WO4 and UT4). Under the maximum energy condition (Figures 2 WO5 and UT5), the fibres could be cut.

From this study, it was concluded that the surface morphology of the laser-treated samples could be controlled by modifying the energy density of the laser radiation. To select the laser-processing conditions for this study, two morphological criteria were established. First, the selected conditions should create as high a

superficial homogeneity as possible. Second, conditions that lead to full fibre exposition, which present high damage risk, should be avoided. In Figure 2, it can be observed that the laser parameters that led to a homogeneously marked resin, fulfilling both the defined requirements, are those that led to the WO1 and UT1 images.

Contact angle measurement

In adhesive bonding, wettability is the most frequently used property to determine the suitability of a plastic surface for bonding. Thus, good wettability of a surface is a prerequisite for good adhesive bonding, and contact angle determination is the most frequently used method for determining the wettability of a solid surface.²⁷⁻³¹ Contact angles below 90° imply high wettability and hence good adhesive behaviour in plastics.

Figure 2. Optical micrographs of woven (WO) and unidirectional tape (UT) samples, acquired at a magnification of 72X and processed with different laser energy densities (H). (1) Marked resin, $H = 116 \text{ J/cm}^2$. (2) Detached resin, $H = 135 \text{ J/cm}^2$. (3) Exposed fibres, $H = 154 \text{ J/cm}^2$. (4) Marked fibres, $H = 174 \text{ J/cm}^2$. (5) Broken fibres, $H = 193 \text{ J/cm}^2$.

To ensure that the laser treatment leads to at least as effective surface activation as manual grinding does, similar or lower contact angles are expected for laser-treated samples. The contact angle measured for the woven (65°) and unidirectional tape (65°) manually ground samples were taken as references.

Selection of laser parameters

To select the laser parameters used to process the samples for mechanical tests, three requirements were defined: processed samples must show only marked resin, as shown in Figure 2 WO1 and UT1; the treated surface must have as high a homogeneous surface aspect as possible; and the samples must show lower contact angles than the reference samples, i.e. lower than 65° for both woven and unidirectional tape. Table 4 gives the laser parameter values that best fulfilled the above requirements for both the woven and unidirectional tape samples.

Figure 3 shows optical micrographs of the surface morphology after laser treatment with the selected laser-processing parameters for woven and unidirectional tape samples. It can be observed that uniform surfaces with marked resin are obtained for both materials.

When comparing data in Table 5, it is observed a decrease of 20% on laser-processed-woven contact angle and of 17% for the laser-processed-unidirectional tape samples, with respect to manually ground samples. This decrease in contact angle implies an improvement of wettability.

Table 4 shows that different materials require different laser parameter values to obtain similar results. The main difference on these parameters are focused on the scanning speed and the angular step, which results in different surface textures observed in Figure 3(c) (laser-treated woven) and 3(f) (laser-treated unidirectional tape). The differences in laser parameters could be related to the different characteristics between woven prepreg and unidirectional tape prepreg, as exposed previously. Further studies are needed to obtain a better understanding of the origin of this phenomenon.

Table 4. Selected laser-processing parameters for woven and unidirectional tape.

Material	Woven	Unidirectional tape
Power	3 W	3 W
Frequency	20 kHz	20 kHz
Speed	1000 mm/s	2000 mm/s
Number of repetitions	2	4
Angular step of radiation	90°	0°

In any case, these results imply the need to perform an experimental study to determine the laser processing parameters for each material.

SEM

Figure 4 shows the SEM images acquired on a woven sample without any superficial treatment and processed with the chosen laser parameters. When comparing SEM images in Figure 4, it can be observed how laser treatment creates a pattern of circular marks on the surface. The treatment is uniform, the sizes of the marks are approximately 50 nm, and the fibres were not affected by this treatment.

Surface roughness

Surface roughness has an important role in relation to adhesiveness. The higher the surface roughness, the better are the adhesive properties of the adherent surface. High surface roughness implies a higher surface contact area between adhesive and adherent. Thus, the selected laser parameters for each material should lead to an increase of surface roughness. Table 6 shows the R_a values measured.

It can be observed how laser treatment significantly increased the surface roughness of the untreated samples, which should enhance the adhesive properties of the surface. Furthermore, it should be noted that the increase of R_a achieved by laser treatment is much higher than that achieved by manual grinding.

XPS

XPS spectroscopy was used to determine the cleaning effect of the UV laser treatment as well as the changes to the surface chemistry caused by laser radiation. To quantify both effects, surface elemental analysis of woven and unidirectional tape for untreated and laser-treated samples was performed via XPS measurements. Furthermore, the cleaning effect of manual grinding was determined. Table 7 includes elemental analysis data calculated from survey XPS spectra, shown in Figure 5, for each material and surface treatment.

Table 7 shows that, in both studied materials, laser treatment removed some elements from the surface, highlighting the cleaning effect of the laser

activation.

From the quantification of the survey spectra, it could be observed that laser treatment completely removed the contaminant species present on the woven sample surface and significantly reduced these contaminants for the unidirectional tape samples. On the other hand, it was also observed how manual

Figure 3. Optical macrographs of (a, b, c) woven and (d, e, f) unidirectional tape samples processed with chosen laser conditions, acquired at the indicated magnifications.

Table 5. Contact angle values for untreated, laser-treated, and manually ground samples for woven and uni-directional tape.

Material	Untreated sample	Manually ground	Laser-treated
Woven	69°	65°	55°
Unidirectional tape	84°	65°	54°

Figure 4. SEM images of: (a) Untreated woven sample. (b) Woven sample treated with the selected laser conditions, described in Table 4. (c) Details of spot in a woven laser treated sample.

Table 6. Surface roughness values (R_a) for untreated, laser-treated and manually ground samples for woven and unidirectional tape.

Material	Untreated sample	Manually ground	Laser-treated
Woven	1.212 mm	0.755 mm	5.350 mm
Unidirectional tape	0.340 mm	0.720 mm	5.960 mm

grinding did not reduce as much Si as laser treatment did. For the woven samples, the atomic concentration of Si even increased. This could be owing to grinding with SiC paper, which can leave contaminants if the surface is not properly cleaned after grinding.

In addition, in Table 7, the values of the O/C and N/C ratios are included. The O/C and N/C ratios

decreased when the surface was laser-treated. This result suggests that the surface reacts chemically with oxygen and nitrogen during the laser activation process. This phenomenon was further confirmed by analysing the high-resolution spectra corresponding to C 1 s, N 1 s and O 1 s, shown in Figure 6.

Table 7. Surface chemical analysis, in atomic percentage, of woven and unidirectional tape samples calculated from XPS surveyspectra of Figure 5.

Sample	Atomic percentage (%)										
	C 1s	N 1s	O 1s	S 2p	Na 1s	Ca 2p	F 1s	Cl 2p	Si 2p	O/C	N/C
WO-UN	70.7	4.9	20.2	1.3	1.5	0.4	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.3	0.07
WO-LT	81.9	4.4	12.3	1.4	N.D.*	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	0.2	0.05
WO-MG	82.3	3.0	12.5	0.8	0.2	0.7	N.D.	N.D.	0.4	0.2	0.04
UT-UN	76.7	4.4	15.9	1.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.5	0.2	0.06
UT-LT	81.3	4.1	12.9	1.3	0.2	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	0.2	0.2	0.05
UT-MG	81.4	4.2	12.9	1.0	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.	0.3	0.2	0.05

WO: woven; UT: unidirectional tape; UN: untreated; LT: laser-treated; MG: manual ground; N.D.: not detected.

Figure 5. XPS survey spectrum for woven and unidirectional tape samples with all surface treatments.

Figure 6. High-resolution XPS carbon (1), nitrogen (2), and oxygen (3) spectra. (a) Untreated woven; (b) laser-treated woven; (c) untreated unidirectional tape; (d) laser-treated unidirectional tape.

Figure 7. Lap shear strength results corresponding to manually ground and laser-treated woven and unidirectional tape samples.

In the high-resolution C 1s spectra for both untreated materials, the three characteristic peaks of epoxy resins could be observed (Figure 6(a1) and (c1)). The main signal at 284.8 eV for both materials corresponds to the hydrocarbon bond C–C. For the woven and tape samples peaks that correspond to C–O and C–N bonds at 286.8 eV and 287.0 eV, respectively, were found. Finally, the signals at 288.6 eV for the woven samples and 288.8 eV for the tape samples correspond to the C–O and COOH bonds.³² Comparing these spectra to those in Figure 6(b1) and

(d1), it can be observed that new functional groups appear after laser treatment. These functional groups caused the transformation of the peak at ≈ 288 eV into two peaks at 287.9 eV and 288.9 eV in the woven samples and at 287.5 eV and 288.7 eV in the tape samples. According to Torrijos et al.,³² these peaks can be assigned to the formation of C=O and O–C=O groups.

Both the positions of the peaks and their relative intensities were affected by laser treatment. As seen in Figure 6(a1) to (d1), those peaks assigned to species

linked to oxygen or nitrogen have higher relative intensities after laser treatment, which implies a higher overall oxidation state of the surface.

High-resolution nitrogen spectra were also collected (Figure 6(a2) to (d2)). In these spectra, the main peak at approximately 399.7 eV, which can be attributed to the amine species, did not undergo any modification in any of the samples. After laser treatment, a second signal of N 1s at approximately 402.2–402.6 eV, appeared. This new peak can be attributed to the partial oxidation of the amino groups.^{33,34} In untreated woven spectrum (Figure 6(a2)), appears a peak at approximately 407 eV, which can be attributed to a nitrogen with high oxidation state, N (V). This specie can be related to some kind of contamination, which is removed with subsequent laser surface treatment (Figure 6(b2)).

Finally, high-resolution O 1s spectra were collected for both materials and treatments and the results are shown in Figure 6(a3) to (d3).

In the case of both untreated materials, the O 1s spectra were dominated by a single peak at 532.3 eV,

which corresponds to C–O and C=O bonds.³⁵ Furthermore, a small feature at 535.8 eV in the O 1s spectrum of the untreated woven material (Figure 6(a3)) can be attributed to the oxygen linked to fluorine.³⁶ After laser treatment, for both materials, the appearance of new peaks can be assigned to formation of carbonyl bonds C=O and further oxidation to carbonate ester O=C–O. For the woven laser-treated samples, peaks corresponding to C=O and carbonate ester O=C–O appeared at 532.0 eV and 534.4 eV, respectively. In the case of unidirectional tape laser-treated samples, the signals corresponding to the carbonyl bond C=O and the carbonate ester O=C–O appeared at 532.1 eV and 534.8 eV, respectively.³²

In short, XPS measurements clearly show that laser treatment allowed for the surfaces of both the woven and unidirectional tape materials to be cleaned and oxidised; in other words, laser treatment led to the surface activation of the samples.

Mechanical tests

The treated samples were bonded and tested to determine the quality of the adhesive joints. These tests enable evaluation of the effectiveness of laser treatment in comparison to manual grinding.

Figure 7 shows the lap shear strength for both materials and surface preparations methods. It can be observed that all obtained results are quite similar and comparable. For the woven samples, laser treatment provided an improvement of 22% with respect to manual grinding. For the unidirectional tape, an improvement in lap shear strength of 7% is observed. For this test, a mean value of bond line thickness of 0.199 mm was measured.

Figure 8. Observed failure modes for lap shear strength test. Mixture of delamination and cohesive modes.

Figure 9. Mode I fracture toughness energy test results corresponding to manually ground and laser-treated woven and unidirectional tape samples.

Figure 10. Observed failure modes for mode I fracture toughness energy test. Mixture of cohesive failure and delamination.

With regard to the failure modes of the lap shear strength test, for woven and unidirectional tape samples, the main modes observed were a mixture of delamination and cohesive failure for both the laser-treated and manually ground samples (Figure 8).

Figure 9 shows the values obtained from the mode I fracture toughness energy test for the woven and unidirectional tape samples.

As in the case of lap shear strength, the mode I fracture toughness energy also showed comparable results between both surface treatments. In this case, the improvements for the woven samples and unidirectional tape were 19% and 22%, respectively. For this test, a mean value of 0.191 mm for the bond line thickness was measured.

In the analysis of the failure in the mode I fracture toughness energy test, the same failure modes were observed for both materials and surface preparation methods, i.e. a mixture of cohesive failure and delamination (Figure 10).

The scattering of the results showed a general trend, wherein scattering was higher for the manually ground samples than for the laser-treated ones, except for laser-treated unidirectional tape samples in the lap shear test. This trend may have been caused by a lack of homogeneity in the manual grinding treatment owing to it being a manual process, in which the results of the treatment depend on the skills of the operator. Laser treatment ensures high reproducibility of results as it is an automatic method in which the effects of treatment remain constant for a set of defined parameters. From the mechanical test results for samples manufactured from woven and unidirectional tape, it can be observed that the laser-activated samples showed slightly better mechanical properties than the manually ground samples. In other words, for these materials, UV laser treatment could be considered as an alternative to the manual grinding process for surface activation prior to adhesive bonding. However, it must be stressed that an individual process for evaluation of the effect of laser radiation on the surface must be performed for each material.

Obtained results are in line with the results observed in various literature.^{8,14,15} Despite the fact that papers

in bibliography do not use the same laser system and materials, the results show that the use of laser technology as a method of surface pre-treatment leads to an improvement of mechanical properties of CFRP adhesive bonded laminates.

Conclusions

UV laser surface activation was studied as a possible alternative to the current method based on a manual grinding process for two different manufactured CFRPs. The influence of various laser parameters was studied. The surface morphology and contact angle values were used as criteria to set the laser-processing conditions. Laser conditions that led to uniform superficial treatments in which marked resin without fibre damage was observed were considered the optimum conditions.

XPS measurements confirmed that the performed treatments led to the removal of some superficial contaminants, mainly F, Cl and Si. In addition, oxidation processes were observed.

Activated samples were joined and underwent mechanical tests for lap shear strength and mode I fracture toughness energy. The results demonstrated that the laser-activated samples showed slightly better adhesive behaviour than the manually activated samples. In addition, the results show less scattering for laser treatment than for manual grinding, which was related to the better repeatability of laser treatment as compared to manual treatments.

Furthermore, the laser-processing conditions were experimentally established for both the studied materials, woven and unidirectional tape. The results demonstrated that the proposed activation method is suitable for different materials; this capability is one of the fundamental conditions that a process must satisfy to be certifiable at the industrial level. However, it is important to note that the laser-processing parameters vary from one material to another. This could be due to the differences in the manufacturing process, fibre areal weight and resin content, all of which could modify the laser-material interaction.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

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